

STUDIES IN THE CYCLOPENTANE SERIES. PART III.* EXPERIMENTS
TOWARDS THE SYNTHESIS OF WIELAND'S C₁₃-ACID IN
PROPER STEREOCHEMICAL FORMS

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A method for the synthesis of 4-(1:5-dimethylhexyl)-5-methyl- Δ^1 -cyclopenten-1:3-dicarboxylic acid is described, which on reduction and the oxidation of the isopropyl group is expected to lead to the desired C₁₃ acid.

In Part I of this series (Dutta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 611), two different routes have been developed for the synthesis of 1-methylcyclopentane-1:2-dicarboxylic acid in different stereoisomeric forms. The one, which appeared to be the most promising at that time, started from $\alpha\delta$ -dibromo- α -methylvaleric acid. Being encouraged by the preliminary success in the case of simple cyclopentane derivative, attention was first directed to apply this method to the synthesis of the following acid.

Unfortunately the attempts in this direction could not be pushed to a successful issue. The results of these investigations have been embodied in Part II (Dutta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 79).

In the second method, ethyl 2-methylcyclopentanone-2-carboxylate has been utilised to synthesise the corresponding cyclopentane dicarboxylic acids. For the present purpose, the corresponding compound should be ethyl 2-methylcyclopentan-3-(1:5-dimethylhexyl)-1-one-2-carboxylate, for which, however, no feasible method of synthesis could then be devised. We are encouraged to reopen this subject after a pretty long time in view of the publication of an interesting paper (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 4) on the synthesis of dihydrojasmine. It utilises the the property of the ready formation of cyclopentenones from γ -lactones on treatment with phosphorus pentoxide.

An analysis of this method leads to the following considerations. If the lactone of the following structure be subjected to this process of ring-closure, two compounds (X, XA) are theoretically possible.

(IX)

(X)

(XA)

The theoretical considerations strongly favour the formation of (X), for the α -hydrogen atom, rendered active by the carbethoxy group, will play its usual part in the forma-

* A preliminary note appeared in *Science & Culture*, 1944, 10, 355.

tion of the carboxylic ring. This contention has been fully substantiated as subsequent investigations will show.

Before proceeding with the main scheme of work, it has been thought desirable to make pilot experiments with more easily available materials. The scheme followed in this case is outlined below.

Ethyl levulinate condenses smoothly with ethyl α -bromopropionate in presence of zinc to give the lactone (I). This on distillation in high vacuum over P_2O_5 leads to the formation of the keto-ester (II) in poor yield (5%), though a considerable portion of the lactone is recovered unchanged. From the nature of the reaction it appears that the formation of the ketone is appreciable in the beginning, but the secondary reactions intervene with considerable tarrification. The unsaturated keto-ester assumes a light green tinge on standing overnight. It absorbs hydrogen catalytically quite readily and the reduced product (III) on hydrolysis gives dimethylcyclopentanone (IV) which is characterised by its boiling point, odour and a well-defined semicarbazone. The formation of (IV) completely rules out the formation of the other theoretical possibility, which would produce under identical conditions an acidic product.

Returning to the main scheme of work, we have synthesised the lactone (IX) by the action of ethyl α -bromopropionate on ethyl ester (VIII) of the long-chain keto-acid (Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 425; *Science & Culture*, 1941-42, 7, 58). The keto-ester (VIII) has been prepared according to Mukherjee with considerable modifications in the various steps of the process. We record briefly the methods of preparation of a few compounds first prepared by him, as some of the physical data are quite at variance with those obtained in the short note published by Mukherjee in the *Science & Culture*. We have also isolated the keto-acid in a solid form melting at $47-48^\circ$.

The *nor*-dihydrocitronelllic acid (VIIA) required in this scheme has been prepared by the condensation of *isohexyl* iodide with ethyl methylmalonate and subsequent hydrolysis. The acid chloride of the above reacts with diazomethane in ethereal solution to give the bromomethyl-ketone (VIIB) (Dutta and Mitter, *Science & Culture*, 1943-44, 9, 505). This condenses with malonic ester and the condensation product (VIIC) on

alkaline hydrolysis and decarboxylation gives the keto-acid (VIII) in a very good yield. Because of the lengthy steps in the synthesis of this acid, we have tried the following scheme.

The two hydrogen atoms in acetoacetic ester can be replaced quite smoothly by isohexyl and methyl groups with the formation of (V) and (VI). The bromination of the disubstituted ester and the condensation of the bromo-ester with ethyl malonate proceeds quite readily. The hydrolysis of the condensation product proved an insurmountable difficulty. Recently an excellent method has been developed by P. C. Mukherjee in our laboratory (private communication) for this purpose.

Another method devised after Cason (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 62, 46) consists of the condensation of the half-ester chloride of succinic acid with methylheptyl magnesium chloride (Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1581) in presence of fused cadmium chloride. No keto-ester could be isolated in this case.

The ethyl ester (VIII) of the keto-acid reacts smoothly with ethyl α -bromopropionate in presence of zinc to give the desired lactone (IX) together with a considerable amount of the high boiling residue. This on heating with P_2O_5 in vacuum gives the unsaturated keto-ester (X) in a very poor yield. It readily takes up hydrogen catalytically to give (XI). On hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube this gives methylisooctylcyclopentanone (XV), the identity of which has been established with that synthesised by Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) through its semicarbazone. The saturated keto-ester (XI) adds up one molecule of hydrocyanic acid and the cyanohydrin (XII) is then dehydrated with an excess of thionyl chloride and pyridine to lead to (XIII) mixed with sulphur compounds, the latter being removed by refluxing with precipitated copper in benzene solution. The unsaturated cyano-ester (XIII) is then hydrolysed by prolonged heating with hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube. The acidic component (XIV) from the product of hydrolysis is isolated in a very poor yield as a thick oil, which does not solidify even on long standing. Unfortunately no suitable solvent could be found to induce its crystallisation. This on reduction of the double bond and oxidation of the isopropyl group is expected to lead to Wieland's C_{11} -acid.

The main scheme of work is graphically represented below :

(In all the formulae $R = -\overset{\text{Me}}{\underset{|}{\text{CH}}}-(\text{CH}_2)_3-\text{CH} : \text{Me}_2$.)

(*iso*-octyl)

Because of the disturbing effect of the *iso*-octyl group in the normal course of reactions, we have developed a new method to introduce the levulinic acid side-chain through a different route and this will form the subject matter of the next communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Lactonic Ester of Ethyl α -Methyl- β -hydroxy- β -methyladipate (I).—Ethyl levulinate (15 g.) was dissolved in benzene (35 c.c.) to which zinc wool (20 g.) and ethyl bromopropionate (18 c.c.) and a crystal of iodine were added. On warming the reaction started and when the vigour of the reaction had subsided (10 minutes) it was heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. On cooling, it was decomposed with ice and acid. The benzene layer was washed with dilute ammonia solution and water. On distillation the lactone passed over at 136°/6 mm., yield 14 g. (Found: C, 60.0; H, 7.6. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0 per cent).

Ethyl 2:3-Dimethyl- Δ^4 -cyclopentenone-2-carboxylate (II).—The above lactonic ester (15 g.) was added to phosphorus pentoxide (8 g.) when the mixture became very hot. Next it was heated in an oil-bath in high vacuum. The product gradually distilled and the distillate was collected (8 g.). It was again distilled and a small fraction (0.5 g.) was collected, which passed over at 90°-95°/6 mm. as a light, clear oil having a characteristic smell and assuming a green colour on standing. The major portion (6 g.) consisted of the unchanged lactone. (Found: C, 65.4; H, 7.3. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 65.9; H, 7.7 per cent).

A portion of the oil was treated with semicarbazide hydrochloride in presence of sodium acetate and the semicarbazone separated after a week in the form of sandy crys-

tals. It crystallised from dilute alcohol as shining crystals with a yellowish tinge. It decomposed at 212-15°.

2:3-Dimethylcyclopentanone (IV).—The above unsaturated ester (0.7 g.) which was freshly distilled, was shaken with hydrogen in presence of platinum catalyst (0.1 g.). Absorption of hydrogen was complete in an hour and the catalyst settled down. It was filtered off and the saturated ester was obtained boiling at 90-92°/6 mm. as a clear, mobile oil having a camphoraceous odour. This ester (0.6 g.) was hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid (conc., 5 c.c.) for 8 hours. On cooling, the solution was extracted with ether thoroughly and on removal of the ether, a small quantity of an oil remained which on distillation gave a fraction (0.2 g.) at 140°-150° and this immediately gave the semicarbazone as shining sandy crystals, m. p. 179-80° after recrystallisation from spirit. (Found: N, 25.4. $C_8H_{15}ON_3$ requires N, 24.8 per cent).

Ethyl isoHexylacetoacetate (V).—Sodium (5.5 g.), dissolved in alcohol (70 c.c.), was treated with acetoacetic ester (32 g.). Next *isohexyl iodide* (50 g.) was added and the solution refluxed for 8 hours. On working up the reaction mixture, the required ester passed over at 120°/9 mm., yield 46 g. (Found: C, 76.5; H, 10.4. $C_{12}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 67.3; H, 10.3 per cent).

Ethyl Methylisohexylacetoacetate (VI).—Sodium salt of the above ester was prepared from sodium (5.6 g.), the ester (45 g.) in benzene (150 c.c.). On treatment with methyl iodide in large excess, a clear mobile liquid boiling at 118°/7 mm. was obtained, yield 31 g. (Found: C, 68.5; H, 10.5. $C_{13}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 68.4; H, 10.4 per cent).

Ethyl δ -isoHexyl- γ -keto-hexoate (VIII).—*nor*-Dihydrocitronellilic acid was prepared in quantity through the condensation of *isohexyl iodide* with *ethyl methylmalonate* and subsequent hydrolysis of the same. The acid chloride, prepared through the action of PCl_5 , was allowed to react with excess of diazomethane in ethereal solution. To the diazo-ketone was added hydrobromic acid and the bromoketone, thus obtained, condensed smoothly with malonic ester to give (VII). This ester (22 g.) was dissolved in spirit (80 c.c.) to which was added caustic potash (12 g.) in water (20 c.c.) and the whole was refluxed for 6 hours, when a clear solution was obtained. Next, alcohol was removed on the water-bath and from the alkaline solution, the dibasic acid was regenerated on acidification and extraction with ether. This on decarboxylation at 190° for about 15 minutes gave the monocarboxylic acid, passing over at 160°-165°/5 mm., yield 14 g. (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*, b. p. 150°/5 mm.). It solidified to long needles, m. p. 47-48°. The ethyl ester was prepared by refluxing the acid (12 g.) with a mixture of alcohol (30 c.c.) and sulphuric acid (1.5 c.c.) for 12 hours on a boiling water-bath. On working up in the usual way, the ethyl ester passed over at 130-32°/5 mm. (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*, b. p. 122°/6 mm.), yield 12 g. (Found: C, 69.7; H, 11.1. $C_{11}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 69.4; H, 10.7 per cent).

Reformatsky's Reaction with the Ester (VIII) and *Ethyl α -Bromopropionate leading to the Lactone* (IX).—This was prepared by heating on the water-bath a mixture of zinc wool (20 g.), the keto-ester (24 g.) and ethyl α -bromopropionate (15 c.c.) and benzene (60 c.c.) in presence of a crystal of iodine. Reaction started after sometime and when the vigour of the initial reaction was over, it was further heated for an hour. On cooling, a further

lot of zinc wool (10 g.) and bromo-ester (10 c.c.) were added and the mixture was refluxed for another hour. The solution became very thick and assumed a light green colour. On working up the mixture, the lactone was obtained boiling at $174^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Mukherjee, b. p. $170^{\circ}/4$ mm.), yield 14 g.

Ethyl 2-Methyl-3-isooctyl- Δ^1 -cyclopentenone-2-carboxylate (X).—The above lactone (IX, 10 g.) was heated in vacuum at 130° - 140° for 10 minutes with phosphorus pentoxide (5 g.). The reaction mixture turned brown. Next it was cooled and decomposed with ice. It was extracted with ether and the ethereal solution was washed with sodium carbonate solution. On working up, a fraction (1.6 g.) was collected at 140° - $155^{\circ}/4$ mm. and the unchanged lactone was recovered at 160° - $170^{\circ}/4$ mm. (5 g.). This was again treated with P_2O_5 (2.5 g.) and worked in the identical way. The combined lower boiling portions (2.5 g.) were redistilled when the keto-ester came over at $145^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 72.4; H, 10.1. $C_{17}H_{28}O_3$ requires C, 72.8; H, 10.1 per cent).

No semicarbazone could be prepared from this keto-ester.

Ethyl 2-Methyl-3-isooctylcyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (XI).—The above unsaturated ester (X, 2.9 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.) and the solution was shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen with platinum oxide (0.2 g.). Absorption of hydrogen was complete in 2 hours (ca. 265 c.c.). It was worked up in the usual way and on distillation it passed over at 150° - $155^{\circ}/8$ mm., yield quantitative. (Found: C, 71.9; H, 10.3. $C_{17}H_{30}O_3$ requires C, 72.3; H, 10.6 per cent).

2-Methyl-3-isooctylcyclopentanone (XV).—The ester (XI, 1.5 g.) was hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid (conc., 10 c.c.) for 36 hours in a sealed tube at 130° - 140° . On working up, a small fraction (0.2 g.) was isolated boiling at 115° - $125^{\circ}/6$ mm. and another fraction came over at higher temperature leaving a considerable quantity of tarry residue in the flask. It was directly converted into semicarbazone which separated slowly as sandy crystals along with an oily matter. On removal of the oily matter on a porous plate, the residue was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 178 - 79° (Mukherjee, b. p. 180 - 81°). (Found: N, 15.0. $C_{15}H_{26}ON_2$ requires N, 15.7 per cent).

5-Methyl-5-carbethoxy-4-isooctyl- Δ^1 -cyclopentenyl Cyanide (XIII).—The above keto-ester (XI, 2.5 g.) was treated at -10° with liquid hydrocyanic acid, generated from potassium cyanide (7 g.) and sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4 , 7 c.c., H_2O , 10 c.c.) in presence of a drop of potassium cyanide solution. The mixture was allowed to stand in an ice-chest overnight. It was then acidified and the excess of hydrocyanic acid was removed in suction. It was extracted with ether and dried thoroughly in vacuum after removal of the solvent. The residue (2.5 g.) was dissolved in pyridine (5 c.c.) and cooled in a freezing mixture. To this was added thionyl chloride (3 c.c.) and the mixture was allowed to stand in ice for an hour. Next, it was heated on the water-bath for 2 hours. The mixture was decomposed with ice and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with acid and alkali and the residue left on evaporation of the solvent was again treated with precipitated copper in benzene solution. On working up in the usual way, the unsaturated cyano-ester was obtained boiling at 145° - $150^{\circ}/2$ mm., yield 1.3 g. The product was slightly yellowish and a few drops of unchanged keto-ester were collected as a forerun. (Found: N, 4.4. $C_{18}H_{26}O_2N$ requires N, 4.8 per cent).

4-isooctyl-5-methyl- Δ^1 -cyclopenten-1:5-dicarboxylic Acid (XIV).— The above unsaturated cyano-ester (XIII, 1.2 g.) was heated with hydrochloric acid (conc., 10 c.c.) in a sealed tube for 12 hours at 130°-140° and for another 12 hours at 150°. There was an appreciable tarrification, and the residue was taken up in ether. The acidic products were washed with sodium bicarbonate solution. On acidification of the alkaline solution, a thick liquid separated out. This was extracted with ether. On removal of the solvent, it was decolorised with animal charcoal in dilute alcoholic solution. On working up, a pale yellow, viscous liquid remained in the flask which could not be converted into solid by keeping in contact with different solvents. The product was, however, free from nitrogen.

Our best thanks are due to Dr. P. C. Mitter, Palit Professor of chemistry (retired) for his kind interest in this piece of investigation. We also take this opportunity of thanking Mr. N. N. Ghosh and Mr. C. N. Bhar for micro-analysis of some the compounds.

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Received September 15, 1947.